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Revisiting Theodor Adorno's Critical Theory and Social Psychology

Somya Tyagi

PhD Research Scholar & Assistant Professor of English,
University of Delhi,
New Delhi.

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Abstract:

This paper examines Frankfurt School Marxist critic, Theodor Adorno's Critical Theory through the lens of his intervention in psychoanalysis, situating his philosophy within a much broader critique of capitalism. Drawing on key works such as *Minima Moralia*, *Dialectic of Enlightenment*, and his reflections on the pathology of the Culture Industry, the paper offers crucial insights into the self-dissolution and conformity of the twentieth-century bourgeois society. It does so while engaging with Adorno's social psychology as a means to diagnose and expose the internalisation of the hegemonic norms. His philosophy, often dismissed as pessimistic, can offer one a positive vision of humanity, one that prioritises the autonomy of art forms and fosters critical reflection. This study emphasises the liberatory potential embedded within Adorno's complex reflections on the irrationality of the administered world.

Keywords: Adorno, Critical Theory, Social Psychology, Culture Industry, Capitalism.

Theodor W. Adorno, a German philosopher and sociologist deeply rooted in Marxist thought, was undoubtedly one of the prominent figures of the Frankfurt School - a group of intellectuals

including Walter Benjamin, Eric Fromm, Herbert Marcuse and Ernst Bloch.¹ They drew upon the ideas of thinkers such as Marx, Freud and Hegel to present a sustained critique of twentieth-century modernity. Adorno, along with his collaborator Max Horkheimer, developed an intellectual tradition known as Critical Theory, a significant form of Marxist thought crucial for interrogating the insidious structures of class, culture and ideology.² As a philosophical movement, Critical Theory gained recognition across numerous institutions and universities globally through various academic settings. Initially founded as the Institute for Social Research in 1923 and affiliated with Goethe University, the group was established consciously to foster Marxist scholarship within Germany. However, with the advent of Nazi regime and consequent persecution of minorities, the institute had to shift its basis to Columbia University, New York City. Critical Theory, which attempted to render a dialectical critique of capitalist culture primarily sought "to liberate human beings from the circumstances that enslave them" (Adorno and Horkheimer 244).

Disillusioned by the failure of Karl Marx's predictions of revolution and its authoritarian turn, the Frankfurt School theorists placed an emphasis on culture by popularising the dialectical method of interrogating societal contradictions. Moreover, they intently focused on the problem of hegemonic rule through ideology and ascertained that technological advancements in communication facilitated this form of rule.³ This was a distinctive brand of neo-Marxist thought whose academic influence was far-reaching. The key philosophical issues of the Frankfurt School

¹ The Institute of Social Research, from which the Frankfurt School originated, was established 1923, in the early years of the Weimar Republic. It survived the Nazi era to become a vibrant center of social theory in the post World-war era.

²The work of more recent members, for instance, Jurgen Habermas, has garnered wide attention throughout North America and Europe.

³ Their novel ideas overlapped with Italian Marxist and scholar Antonio Gramsci's theory of cultural hegemony.

include the critique of capitalist society, ideological liberation, and the diagnosis of societal pathologies. Critical Theory elaborates on certain central political and economic concepts like reification, commodity fetishization along with a vehement denunciation of mass-culture. Rejecting the orthodox ideas of Soviet Communism, the Frankfurt School studies combined Marxist analysis along with Freudian psychoanalysis to formulate the basis of Critical Theory. Hence, Theodor Adorno's works may be viewed as an attempt to forge a Marxist theory of twentieth-century capitalism and considering the pessimistic image that he paints of contemporary society – an analysis of the limited remaining possibilities that endure in arts and philosophy for keeping politically committed and critical thought alive.

Born in Frankfurt am Main, son of the merchant Oscar Wiesengrund and singer Maria Calvelli-Adorno, Adorno developed a deep affinity to classical music. He was quite intellectually gifted during his formative years. As a classically trained pianist, influenced by Schoenberg's compositional methods, Adorno grounded much of his subsequent works in his profound dedication to avant-garde musical forms. During his education, Adorno encountered anti-Semitism, which left a lasting imprint on his intellectual make-up and later writings as well. Having completed his doctoral studies on Husserl's phenomenology at Frankfurt University in 1924, he later joined as a professor at the same university. His writings span a range of disciplines, including sociology, philosophy, psychology, cultural criticism, and musicology. This range reflects Adorno's engagement with major philosophers such as Hegel, Kant, Husserl and Kierkegaard. However, under the Nazi regime, owing to his half-Jewish origin, he turned a refugee, and fled Germany to seek refuge in America. While in the States, he collaborated on varied research projects, for instance, on studies around the 'Authoritarian Personality' and 'Culture Industry'. During this time, he published his most poignant work *Dialectic of*

Enlightenment (1947) in collaboration with friend Max Horkheimer. His cultural critique impinges on the recessive social transformations conditioned by the rise of mass culture industry. He reflects on the standardization of all human relations in the capitalist society. *Enlightenment as Mass Deception* is a pivotal essay which was initially published in *Dialectic of Enlightenment*. It defines the culture industry as a factory that produces standardized and homogenous art-works, literature and cinema. This industry does not create real value or encourage spiritual growth, rather serves as an effective tool for manipulating the passive consumers. Thus, the use value of a product is replaced by exchange value through 'commodity fetishisation'.⁴

As cultural objects become more interchangeable due to the all-pervasive effects of capitalism, they decline in significance and consequently lose their 'aura'. Adorno's pessimistic philosophy attempts to convince us of the pathology of modern culture and the pitfalls of not resisting the cultural hegemony of late capitalist society. Adorno had vociferously argued that the "wrong life cannot be lived rightly" (Adorno, *Minima Moralia* 39). In his scathing critique of popular culture, he insists that masses under capitalism suffer the same fate as art works under the impact of culture industry. They are reduced to their exchange value with no intrinsic traits as the Enlightenment tradition had hoped for. Adorno critiqued the propensity among the populace of advanced industrial societies to submit to the aforementioned politics and cultural hegemony instead of seeking their rational interests. Theorising that objective laws are no longer tenable, and that psychology has failed in providing insights into the fractured psychic state of people under modernity, Adorno argues that psychoanalysis remains an enigma. He grapples with the problem like an adept sociologist while uncovering the insidious psychological base of fascism. The real

⁴ A fetish is an inanimate object invested with autonomous divine powers by the worshippers. Karl Marx termed this illusory autonomy of the object as 'commodity fetishism'.

subversive potential of Adorno's social psychology lies in resisting the irrational violence of the administered world and in comprehending the objective conditions that were accountable for such regressive subjectivity. Contrary to the tragic tendency of totalitarian violence and the annihilation of the autonomous subject, Adorno's social psychology becomes a theory of praxis with the potential for possible resistance to the aforementioned barbarity of modernity. Adorno's intervention in Freudian psychoanalytical theories through his work on social psychology and 'negative dialectics' may provide us insightful ways of perceiving 'neurosis' not simply as a debilitating condition or damaged modern subjectivity, but perhaps, signalling the historical suffering under modern conditions, and a quest for happiness, even if in the negative.

Dialectic of Enlightenment illuminates the predicament of modern living under the apparently 'rational' Enlightenment values and examines popular culture to proclaim that all art forms have been reduced to mere "business" (Adorno and Horkheimer 95). This irrationality, however, was embedded within the notion of 'reason' itself, thereby facilitating totalitarian regimes and consequently disempowering the masses.⁵ Far from being a means of self-development, mass culture was in actuality its antithesis, one that appeals only to the self-indulgent populace. Thus, the book offers a scathing critique of modernity to diagnose how rationalized modernity is implicated with barbarism. However, it continually imagines itself free from its strangleholds. Frankfurt School theorists saw through the facade and proclaimed that mass culture was a threat to the art's autonomy and integrity. Hence, they challenged the status quo vehemently. The totalitarian regimes are controlled by instrumental rationality, wherein the Holocaust atrocities had permitted humanity to dominate nature at the expense of an individual's place within the natural world. Though in no way is this critical analysis of the culture industry a direct

⁵ Adorno elucidates how mass consumption is often controlled and influenced through advertising or media.

denunciation of commerce, Adorno's writings bear testimony to the uncritical modes of thinking that individuals inevitably adopt under capitalism. Underneath this bleak picture of the culture industry, there is a subtle attempt to regain the lost organic totality of society.⁶ But, above all, Adorno's philosophy is focused on urging us to critically discern modern culture's pathology before the industry's complete appropriation of their private life. To liberate oneself from the negativity of Culture Industry, re-reading a psychosomatic disorder such as neurosis in a more redemptive light could be both subversive and one way to deal with it. Adorno's *Negative Dialectics* challenges the traditional form of Hegelian dialectic. It is formulated at the level of individual as well as collective psychology to overcome both individual and social suffering. As he notes in his philosophical reflections in *Minima Moralia* -

The only philosophy which can be responsibly practiced in face of despair is the attempt to contemplate all things as they would present themselves from the standpoint of redemption. Knowledge has no light but that shed on the world by redemption: all else is reconstruction, mere technique (Adorno, *Minima Moralia* 153).

In *Dialectic of Enlightenment*, Adorno argues that historical evidence bears testimony to how science, reason and logic have transformed into mere mythic irrationality under modern conditions. This inevitable alienation between man and nature has been accelerated by industrialisation. The idea of pseudo-individuality marketed by the culture industry reduces human beings to the status of an object. While the Nazi regime represented an entirely novel form of government, totalitarian regimes employed irrational terror to exterminate entire categories of innocent Jewish population. Moreover, as Adorno insists, the pervasiveness of an egocentric

⁶ Divided in five chapters, this work deals with significant issues such as critique of the culture industry, myth and enlightenment, and anti-Semitism.

bourgeois attitude in public life contributed hugely towards making totalitarianism viable. Despite being pessimistic in its tone, the text expresses optimism that the modern individual can use the tools Enlightenment offers to counter instrumental reason and, hence, divert humanity from its dangerous path toward self-destruction. On the contrary, Walter Benjamin fathomed technology's significance in the highly industrialised societies of the twentieth century, and commented on the massive expansion of the media. In his poignant essay *The Work of Art in the Age of Mechanical Reproduction* (1935), Benjamin insists that modern technological innovations have radically transformed the idea of a work of art. He argues that the rise of media and technology had the potential to do away with the traditional ritualistic value of literature and offer it a subversive political freedom. Technology enables art to be mechanically reproduced in several ways. It makes art works available to the masses which was earlier a prerogative of the elite. Benjamin advocated for the democratisation of media and arts inherent in the advancement of mechanical reproduction. This facilitated the involvement of masses in both culture and politics. He terms it as the withering of "aura" or the liquidation of the traditional value of the cultural heritage (Benjamin, *Work of Art* 47). This theory was indispensable for the formulation of certain revolutionary demands concerning the politics of art under totalitarian regimes.

Adorno possessed an intense awareness of mass culture's potential to mould society, and so, objected to the aforesaid philosophy terming it as a simple 'romanticization' of art. He saw media and technology colluding with populism to cement the hegemonic status quo. Hence, Adorno turned to an analysis of Freudian psychoanalysis for a more thorough account of the unconscious as a product of the varied intertwining psychological as well as social processes. He rejected Sigmund Freud's suggestion in his *Introductory Lectures* that psychosomatic disorders could be treated through therapy and that happiness could be restored via productive capability. Both

sociology and psychology needed to be more introspective, self-reflective and self-critical. In a capitalist society that offers its consumers no real choice, Adorno argues that psychology's failure to comprehend why individuals submit to cultural and political domination against their interests is quite evident. Hence, to counter it, he instead advocates for his brand of 'social psychology' that does not shun the negativity of society as it truly is. Claiming that pure or undamaged art forms no longer exist in a world ridden by irrational violence, he theorises that autonomous art forms can still resist their appropriation into the capitalist forms of production. Adorno argues that "no science has yet explored the inferno in which were forged the deformations that later emerge to daylight as cheerfulness, openness, sociability, successful adaptation to the inevitable, an equable, practical frame of mind" (Adorno, *Minima Moralia* 59). Through his social psychology, Adorno finds in 'neurosis' a subversive category that can address the truth of the absence of collective happiness. Neurosis registers the real lived suffering and trauma of modernist individuals and therefore turns into a positive or healing force by offering us tools to re-examine our fractured consciousness.

Adorno's brand of social psychology serves a dual purpose, wherein it both seeks to enhance our understanding of human behaviour and instincts that shape it, as well as meditate on the underlying ideological forces that inform our drives. His writings are a devastating indictment of the deformities of our age and the banality of mass culture. He reflects on the cultural logic of late capitalism to investigate the insidious permeation of rationalized time into every aspect of human life. Thus, culture inevitably loses its spontaneity as a means of organic expression for the masses but is rendered an entity in the hands of the ruling classes to manipulate them. Consequently, there is an erasure of the capacity for any progressive individual imagination or autonomy. The culture industry is complicit with the capitalist society and its arbitrary dictates. Capitalism ascribes to

each commodity an exchange value, leading to America's foremost Marxist critic, Fredric Jameson's conception of 'reification' or the degeneration of all human rational and creative abilities. However, the enthusiastic participation of masses in the industry reflects not merely their uncritical mindset. It reflects their prudence in aligning themselves with the status quo that demands their unequivocal submission. While these commodities seem to carry unique traits, they are, in fact, identical and bereft of a spiritual core. The aforesaid implies a total negation of freedom that inevitably leads us to interrogate the larger issues of freedom and autonomy as promoted by the so-called bourgeois 'democratic' states.

The argument expressed by Adorno in *Dialectic of Enlightenment* is related to another philosophical work written during his exile from Germany, *Minima Moralia* (1951), translated as *Minima Moralia: Reflections on a Damaged Life* (1974). It is a philosophical record of despair of the fractured psychic life of individuals under modernity during and post the Second World War, and of the faint hope for revolutionary change in the capitalist world order. The bourgeois society is run by capitalist logic, which is inherently exploitative. Under this process, the property owner appropriates the surplus goods produced by the working class, who, as wage earners, are a part of the bourgeois society, but who are simultaneously kept out of it because they are not the owners. Workers own nothing but their labour, which they must sell to the marketplace. Thus, we witness their inevitable alienation from the products of their labour. The intellectual claim for the emancipation of bourgeois society, Adorno insisted, is marked by umpteen contradictions. According to him, philosophy's attempt to silence the critique it had itself unleashed rendered social psychology an indispensable tool to combat society's identification with the status quo. The World Wars, Holocaust and forced exile from Germany were agonising experiences that had led to the discrepancy between individual existence and social frameworks. Thus, any objective claim

to a rationally structured fusion of society had been distorted into absurdity by the irrationality of society. The very possibility of a meaningful life is blocked. According to Adorno, "The very people who burst with proofs of exuberant vitality could easily be taken for prepared corpses..." (Adorno, *Minima Moralia* 59). Through such particular negative insights, Adorno aimed at overcoming prevailing societal negativity as negation could bring some consolation to the damaged life of the modern individual.

Adorno's unsettling account of anti-semitism also provides a crucial entry point into an analysis of authoritarian irrationalism. The ethnic prejudice of anti-semitism can be read as a metonym for the more general mechanisms of prejudice and collective scapegoating of minorities characteristic to different environments. Freudian theory heavily influenced the account of authoritarianism developed by Adorno. The dynamics of fascist regimes, and its dangerous propaganda were conceptualized almost exclusively in psychoanalytic terms in his works. The aforesaid elucidates how the self is shaped and reshaped by the historical, social and cultural conditions. In late modern society that thrives on the repetitive formula of mass culture, the hope of viewing an individual as free and autonomous is an absolute anachronism. For Adorno, mass culture and fascism work hand in hand and feed off each other to produce passive, child-like dependency of their consumers. Advertisements, soap operas, and astrology columns are all fascist propaganda with common characteristics, wherein they operate by fostering dependency and pseudo needs in the masses. The central motif underlying Adorno's philosophy is that a better world can be conceived only through the negation of society's existing negativity. In the light of the triumph of totalitarianism and fascism, it became crucial to ascertain why the human condition was tumbling into a new kind of barbarism. Under late capitalism, considering the psychological constitution of individual subjects

and possible signs of their suffering, neuroticism could be read as the rejection of civilisation as well as the embodiment of its dynamism.

From an Adorno-esque perspective, the culture industry makes tremendous profits by churning out the ever-same rubbish in the form of art, films, music, etc. Moreover, it helps a system of power like capitalism succeed by manipulating the consumers and distracting them from ascertaining the manifest injustices of the world. The psychic wounds of individuals in modernity, Adorno argues, can offer us the possibility of a critique of culture and can be taken as signs or indicators of possible collective liberatory happiness. Hence, in Adorno's philosophical reflections, we find his insistence on neuroticism as a register of historical trauma, one that emanated from the solidification of capitalist society. Adorno notes,

Society has, as it were, assumed the sickness of all individuals, and in it, in the pent-up lunacy of Fascist facts and all their innumerable precursors and mediators, the subjective fate buried deep in the individual is integrated with its visible objective counterpart. And how comfortless is the thought that the sickness of the normal does not necessarily imply as its opposite the health of the sick, but that the latter usually only present, in a different way, the same disastrous pattern. (Adorno, *Minima Moralia* 59)

To truly reconcile oneself to the pathology of modernity and its dissatisfaction, the individual's lack of adjustment to societal mores turns into a sign of reason, and perhaps, one of the very few ways of untangling oneself from the toxic cultural logic of late capitalism. Adorno lauded the modernist writings of Franz Kafka and Samuel Beckett for their uncompromising presentation of modern psychological fragmentation. In their bleak narratives, replete with themes of neuroticism, absurdity and alienation, Adorno recognised a greater fidelity to the truth of capitalism. Adorno

believed that such autonomous artworks could expose the reality and structural negativity of the world. Their art does not seek to find solutions to contradictions but depicts its unmediated form, which could turn into healing forces. Such a hopeful interpretation aligns more closely with the real spirit of Adorno's philosophy than the reductive, condemnatory readings stereotypically associated with his works.

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